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Impact of Self Financing Institutions on Sustainable Development Goals, SDG4

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**Sanjeev Kumar
Chadha**

Professor
Department Of Law
SLS, Babasaheb Bhimrao
Ambedkar Central
University
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Kamal Rajora

Research Scholar
Department Of Law
SLS, Babasaheb Bhimrao
Ambedkar Central
University
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

“It is our moment to galvanize international support for education as the world prepares to adopt a new set of Sustainable Development Goals to guide the struggle to achieve a life of dignity for all.... To turn promises into action, we have to mobilize resources.”

Ban Ki-moon, Secretary-General, United Nations

Knowledge is the driving force in the rapidly changing globalised economy and society. Quantity and quality of highly specialized human resources determine their competence in the global market. Emergence of knowledge as driving factor results in both challenges and opportunities. It is now well recognized that the growth of the global economy has increased opportunities for those countries with good levels of education and vice versa. The benefits of globalization accrue to the countries with highly skilled human capital and it is a curse for the countries without such specialized human capital. Developing and transition countries are further challenged in a highly competitive world economy because their higher education systems are not adequately developed for the creation and use of knowledge. Converting the challenges into opportunities depend on the rapidity at which they adapt to the changing environment. Though the higher education system and the pattern of financing higher education vary a great deal across countries in terms of their size and strength and degree of diversification of higher education institutions, yet they all face a severe financial crisis in the public finances available for higher education.[1]

It is now well understood that, on average, countries with higher levels of growth have labour forces with higher levels of formal schooling. With the shift to an information economy, globalization and flexible organizations of production, these arguments are further reinforced. The arguments that link high levels of education are linked not only to scientifically trained manpower but to higher levels of general education.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence and Patent Laws in India: An Analysis of Challenges Before Law

Introduction

India's higher education system is the third largest in the world. It is the education system where lakhs of students enroll themselves every year for the purpose of getting quality education both from India and abroad. Higher education in Indian context implies the education which starts after the completion of secondary education and this education imparts at the colleges and universities. It is higher education that lays importance on the development of knowledge in the students and creation of new perspectives in different areas to have a wider view of the world. Higher education in India is considered as an input which helps in the growth and development of intellectual manpower, industries, agricultural achievement and creation of precious resource that help in the overall progress of the country in various fields. Higher education would also contribute directly or indirectly to the establishment of the country as a power among the nations of the world.

The higher education system sits at the apex of the education system, supporting the lower levels of education, preparing professionals and skilled labour, and serving as an incubator for research. As developing countries expand basic education systems and increasingly transition into the knowledge economy, higher education will play an important role, as acknowledged in the Sustainable Development Goals, serving as an incubator for the knowledge base and human capital needed to promote and sustain development across many sectors. Although it is reasonable to regard education a fundamental source of economic growth, spending on education is also facilitated by the growth of national income. In the developing countries, constraints on public resources and current economic conditions have reduced most governments' ability to provide adequate funding for further expansion of the educational system, in particular at the higher level. The demand for education at every level is rapidly increasing. However, funds for education are not increasing at a commensurate level resulting into the widening gap.

Objective of study

Objective of this paper is to study the impact of self financing institutions on sustainable development goals.

Review of Literature

SDG 4: Quality Education

The Sustainable Development Goals – an ambitious and universal agenda to transform our world On 25 September 2015, the UN General Assembly adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2015). This new global framework to redirect humanity towards a sustainable path was developed following the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20) in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil in June 2012, in a three-year process involving UN Member States, national surveys engaging millions of people and thousands of actors from all over the world. At the core of the 2030 Agenda are 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The universal, transformational and inclusive SDGs describe major development challenges for humanity[2].

The aim of the 17 SDGs is to secure a sustainable, peaceful, prosperous and equitable life on earth for everyone now and in the future. The goals cover global challenges that are crucial for the survival of humanity. They set environmental limits and set critical thresholds for the use of natural resources. The goals recognize that ending poverty must go hand-in-hand with strategies that build economic development. They address a range of social needs including education, health, social protection and job opportunities while tackling climate change and environmental protection[3]. The SDGs address key systemic barriers to sustainable development such as inequality, unsustainable consumption patterns, weak institutional capacity and environmental degradation. For the goals to be reached, everyone needs to do their part: governments, the private sector, civil society and every human being across the world. Governments are expected to take ownership and establish national frameworks, policies and measures for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda[4].

A key feature of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is its universality and indivisibility. It addresses all countries – from the Global South and the Global North – as target countries[5]. All countries subscribing to the 2030 Agenda are to align their own development efforts with the aim of promoting prosperity while protecting the planet in order to achieve sustainable development. Thus, with respect to the SDGs, all countries can be considered as developing and all countries need to take urgent action.

The importance of education is not limited to its potential to combat poverty and realise other human rights. As the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights states, “a well-educated, enlightened and active mind, able to wander freely and widely, is one of the joys and rewards of human existence”. Education is also a human right in itself. The right to education for all and without discrimination has been recognised by a large number of international treaties and States have an obligation to protect and fulfil this right.

SDG 4 sets specific targets to address these challenges and provides a comprehensive framework to achieve inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Beyond enrolment rates, SDG 4 puts a welcomed emphasis on quality education and learning outcomes. The targets cover lifelong education from early childhood development to university and vocational training. Special attention is also given to eliminating gender disparities and ensuring equal access to education for vulnerable children[6].

Main Text

**Objectives For SDG 4 “Quality Education”
Cognitive learning objectives**

1. The learner understands the important role of education and lifelong learning
2. opportunities for all (formal, non-formal and informal learning) as main drivers of sustainable development, for improving people's lives and in achieving the SDGs.
3. The learner understands education as a public good, a global common good, a fundamental human right and a basis for guaranteeing the realization of other rights.
4. The learner knows about inequality in access to and attainment of education, particularly between girls and boys and in rural areas, and about reasons for a lack of equitable access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities.
5. The learner understands the important role of culture in achieving sustainability.
6. The learner understands that education can help create a more sustainable, equitable and peaceful world.

Socio-emotional learning objectives

1. The learner is able to raise awareness of the importance of quality education for all, a humanistic and holistic approach to education, ESD and related approaches.
2. The learner is able through participatory methods to motivate and empower others to demand and use educational opportunities.
3. The learner is able to recognize the intrinsic value of education and to analyse and identify their own learning needs in their personal development.
4. The learner is able to recognize the importance of their own skills for improving their life, in particular for employment and entrepreneurship.
5. The learner is able to engage personally with ESD.

Behavioural learning objectives

1. The learner is able to contribute to facilitating and implementing quality education for all, ESD and related approaches at different levels.
2. The learner is able to promote gender equality in education.
3. The learner is able to publicly demand and support the development of policies promoting free, equitable and quality education for all, ESD and related approaches as well as aiming at safe, accessible and inclusive educational facilities.
4. The learner is able to promote the empowerment of young people.
5. The learner is able to use all opportunities for their own education throughout their life, and to apply the acquired knowledge in everyday situations to promote sustainable development

India's Journey Towards Achieving The Sustainable Development Goals

For India to achieve all targets of Goal 4 of the SDGs within a 15 year time frame, QAEI offer a window of opportunity to be the pre requisites for quality and accessibility of education for India's young population to achieve at least a minimum proficiency level in reading and maths and at the same time be productive and skilled workforce for the resurgent India. However, series of programmes and policies initiated by India, focussing on quality and inclusiveness are already in place prior to the 10 adoption of SDGs[7]. In India, Constitutionally several key programmes and policies have been initiated to provide free and compulsory education to all children in the age group of six to fourteen years as a Fundamental Right. The Ministry of Human Resource Development works through two departments viz. Department of School Education and Literacy responsible for universalizing elementary education and Department of Higher Education engaged in establishing world class institutions of higher learning. India follows four stages of school education programme, in which pre-primary education is not a part of the formal education structure. An initiative like the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) provides for inclusive elementary education for all and reserved 25 percent quotas in private schools for children from economically weaker sections (EWS) of the society. Education for inclusion specifically intended to give equal opportunities for all sections of society that includes gender, SC/ST, minorities, migrants, out of school children and children with special needs, require strong government intervention[8].

Sources of Higher Education In India

Governmental Bodies: In India, education is included in the concurrent list i.e. education is considered as the joint responsibility of both center and the state. The government funds are created and distributed through its various agencies like UGC, NCERT, NCTE, NUEPA, AICTE, SCERT etc. The central government of India has been framing several policies and schemes and the state government is required to implement those in every now and then. Apart from that both the central and state government jointly frame enormous schemes to uplift the financial provisions of the students in the form of scholarships, fellowships etc. Local bodies: In managing education, local bodies also furnish as an important means of financial help whenever necessary. Different local

bodies like Zila Parishad, Panchayat Samities Nagar Panchayats, Gram Panchayats, Municipalities and Corporations etc. are working for the fulfilment of educational goals in the higher educational institutions at the grass root level[9].

Private Funds: Private funds denotes the funds which are allocated through the donations, subscriptions, gifts, bequests, fines, sale proceeds, interest on bank balances, rent from buildings etc. These are also called public philanthropy. Private funds for the higher educational institutions also include those institutions which are run by the private bodies and thus funds are generated through their own income accumulated from various sources.

Grant-in-Aid: Grants are provided by the government or through its various agencies to the higher educational institutions. The financial help or contribution in the form of money or material goods by a bigger government to a smaller unit of it is called a grant. These grants may be provided with a periodical payment or one time basis by focusing on a specific area under the heads like classified grant, compensatory grant, multiple grants, the negotiable and hoc grant etc.

Fees: The fees are collected from the students in return of the tuition or other services provided to them in the educational institution. Fees generally includes admission fees, tuition fees, library fees, examination fees, fees collected for co-curricular activities, laboratory fees, electricity fees etc.

Endowment and Land Grant: Religious institutions and other organizations or NG's keep aside some part of their collected money or income for the purpose of spending in education and these organizations donate this amount of money for the welfare of educational institutions and hence the endowed colleges or educational institutions get benefitted from such endowments. Endowment funds, gifts, donations and other such type of voluntary contributions from individuals or firms, factories, temples, churches etc. are included in the income from endowments for the educational institutions[10].

Other Sources Of Income: The higher educational institutions also generate income from donations, gifts, subscriptions, fines, money from rents, loans, debts. etc. and all these are included in the other sources of income.

Financing in the higher education sector has undergone tremendous changes from the initial years to till date, which is due to the recommendations of different committees and commissions formed time to time. For instance, a few can be mentioned: during the post independence period, the Commission on University Education has recommended educational finance policy, Kothari Commission (1964-66) recommended issues specific to states in financing education, National Policy of Education (1986) recommended allocation of resources and financial management, Justice Punnaya Committee report (1992-93) recommended UGC funding of HEIs and cost sharing by increasing fees, National Knowledge Commission (2006) has recommended improved management of higher education and promotion of intellectual property rights, N.R. Narayana Murthy Committee reported corporate sector participation in the higher education sector for maximizing market participation for improving efficiency and autonomy (Panigrahi, 2018) [11].

Expenditure on Education in India

The Union Budget for 2024-25 has allocated ₹1,20,628 crore to the Ministry of Education, reflecting a 7% decrease from the revised estimate of ₹1,29,718 crore for 2023-24. This decrease is a continuation of the trend where the overall education budget falls short of the National Education Policy (NEP) target of 6% of GDP[12].

The budget includes new initiatives but also reveals significant reductions, especially in higher education. Funding for higher education has been cut by 17%, while school education has seen a marginal increase. The budget's new schemes and investments in digital infrastructure are aimed at enhancing educational quality, but the reductions have raised concerns about their potential impact.

While India has made significant strides in improving access to education, challenges remain in terms of quality, infrastructure, and equitable distribution of resources. Over the past decade, India's education spending has hovered between 3 per cent and 4 per cent of GDP, with fluctuations depending on economic conditions and government priorities[13].

According to the World Bank data, in 2023, the US allocated 6 per cent of its total GDP to education. Meanwhile, neighboring China allocated slightly more, dedicating 6.13 per cent of its GDP to education during the same period[14].

Japan invested 7.43 per cent of its GDP in education. In contrast, India allocated only 4.6 per cent of its total GDP to education in its interim Budget for FY25[15].

Self Financing Education in India

First of all self financing concept makes the education a salable commodity. Only rich people can purchase it and have-nots should go back. Thus an artificial rich and poor divide is created in the society, that too in the young minds of children. It is dangerous for the country in the long run.

Do not believe the government has no money to start educational institutions. They are wasting crores of rupees on unnecessary and luxury projects. Instead of giving priority to people's basic needs, they have other priorities to satisfy the creamy layer of the society. Just to remind you - a sample: The Government of India has written off Rs. 10,57,000 crores of bad loans in the last 5 years[16].

SFEI promotes international standards is a myth, a claim that's all. In the majority of developed countries education is provided by government institutions only, not by self financing institutes, and they achieved the so called international standards! That means even rich countries are giving free education to all its citizens, why a poor country like India should deny it to its people?

The idea of both private and government institutions coexisting is a failure idea. When Pundit Nehru introduced the mixed economy of public sector and private sector industries in India, shortly after Independence, his critics cautioned him it is like the adulteration of originals with duplicates! They were proved right as public sector institutions were destroyed over the decades by corruption, red-tapism, conspiracy, and negligence, mainly because of the influence parallel private sector has with the government. Readers might have experienced, while waiting for a government bus on a bus stand, that it will not come in time, or a dirty 'dappa' bus may arrive just one minute before, if there is a private bus next. People used to murmur; persons concerned are paid for this episode. Thus, almost all government ventures will run in losses or badly if there is a private venture in the same field. This is true even with educational institutions.

Are they not best private educational institutions in India started even before independence? Yes, it is true. But the major difference is they were established by Philanthropic individuals, families, Christian missions or trusts[17]. They impart education free of cost as a social service. On the contrary, present day self financing institutions are money minded to the core, thrive on money looted from students. Slowly they are closing down free or aided courses and starting self financing courses with different title in its place. That's why self financing concept is referred as pathogens, spreading deadly disease. Now money alone determines the education from pre KG to PhD. If you have money you can purchase any degree in India[18].

What we see now as bad in government institutions are all due to step motherly treatment, insufficient funds and supervisions and corruption in government. They all can be corrected by vigilant parents and people once students from rich and poor, educated and illiterate families are admitted to the same school. Of late only students from poor families alone studying in government schools and colleges and hence all the problems crept in there. Educated, rich and influential parents will look after the welfare of schools their wards are studying.

In SEFI children are segregated from the real world and they are not exposed to poverty ridden poor children. Hence they lose characters like empathy, philanthropy, helping tendency, etc as almost all their classmates are from rich families, instead, they develop stubborn, rough and rude attitude. It is well known that SFEI are paying only one fourth or one third of the salary of government teachers. Hence all best brains are aspiring and joining government services after passing competitive examinations written by lakhs of people[19].

Decline in Public Funding for Education

The present government's drive for privatisation and commercialisation of education involves deep cuts in public funding for education.

Figure shows a declining trend of Budget expenditure of Ministry of Education from approximately 4% in 2013-14 to less than 2% in 2024-25. Moreover, there is a tendency for revised estimates of public expenditure on education to less than the Budget estimates (BE) reflecting a gap between reality and promise in this regard.

Figure 1: Expenditure of Ministry of Education (Rs crore)

Note: BE – Budgeted Estimate and RE – Revised Estimate
Source: Union budget documents of various years; PRS.

As far as the higher education sector is concerned, the revised estimate (RE) was Rs. 57,245 crore in 2023-24, which declined by 17% (Rs. 9,625 crore) to Rs. 47,620 crore in 2024-25. The breakup of this decline in public expenditure among different segments of higher education needs to be examined[20].

The UGC (University Grants Commission) budget meant for general education has sharply declined by 61% from Rs. 6,409 crore, as per the RE in 2023-24 to Rs. 2,500 crore BE in 2024-25[21].

The budget allocation for the All-India Council for Technical Education, meant for technical and professional education, has stagnated at Rs. 400 crore in these years, which amounts to a real decline, taking into account an average annual rate of inflation of 5%.

The MUSK amount has not been apportioned to any scheme for education in 2023-24. MUSK is a non-lapsable fund in which proceeds of secondary and higher education cess are credited, to be utilised for schemes in secondary and higher education.

In 2024-25, the MUSK budget was Rs. 5,000 crore reflected as a part of grants to Central universities, and if we add the Higher Education Finance Agency (HEFA) loans allocation of Rs. 372 crore, then this amounts to Rs. 5,372 crore. Therefore, the grants allocated to Central Universities net of MUSK and HEFA, declined by 16% to Rs. 10,100 crore in nominal terms during 2024-25 in comparison to 2023-24.

The fund allocation to Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) moderately increased in nominal terms from Rs. 9,292 crore to Rs. 9,635 crore over these years but declined in real terms, taking into account an annual rate of inflation of 5%.

Thus, there is a declining trend of public funding in higher education institutions and diversion of funds toward either loans or MUSK (not used by the institutions) is a great concern for social well-being of the society.

Impact of Self Financing Education

Self-financing higher education in India, introduced as a means to augment financial resources for educational institutions, has led to several unintended consequences. While intended to alleviate financial burdens, this model has raised concerns regarding educational quality, faculty qualifications, infrastructure adequacy, and equitable access.

1. Deterioration of Educational Quality

The proliferation of self-financing courses has often compromised the quality of education. Many institutions prioritize revenue generation over academic excellence, leading to: **Inexperienced Faculty:** To minimize costs, institutions frequently hire underqualified or temporary faculty. For instance, in Himachal Pradesh, government colleges offering self-financing courses rely heavily on contract or guest faculty, with none recruiting regular staff as per AICTE norms[22].

- **Inadequate Infrastructure:** Despite substantial fee collections, institutions often lack essential facilities. In Odisha, universities offering self-financing courses face poor infrastructure and faculty shortages, leading to student dissatisfaction and protests.
- **Overcrowded Classes:** To maximize revenue, some colleges admit excessive numbers of students, resulting in overcrowded classrooms and compromised individual attention. In Tamil Nadu, certain government-aided colleges have expanded self-financing sections without proportional infrastructure or faculty, raising concerns about educational quality.

2. Financial Exploitation and Lack of Transparency

Self-financing courses often involve higher fees without corresponding improvements in educational quality. This scenario leads to:

- **Capitation Fees:** Some institutions charge exorbitant capitation fees under the guise of donations, adding substantial financial burdens on students. These fees are sometimes not accounted for transparently, leading to financial exploitation.
- **Fee Disparities:** There's a significant fee gap between self-financing and government-funded courses. For example, in Lucknow, self-financing courses can cost students Rs 15,000-25,000 per year, several times the Rs 4,000-5,000 for subsidized courses, without proportional enhancements in facilities or faculty quality.

3. Erosion of Academic Standards

The emphasis on revenue generation over academic rigor has led to:

- **Admission of Underprepared Students:** To fill seats, some institutions admit students with poor academic records, resulting in a student body that may lack the foundational knowledge necessary for rigorous academic work.
- **Substandard Faculty Recruitment:** Financial constraints lead institutions to hire faculty without prioritizing experience or subject matter expertise, adversely affecting teaching quality. In many self-financing courses operate without a single regular faculty member, relying entirely on temporary staff.

4. Infrastructure Deficiencies

Despite collecting substantial fees, many self-financing courses lack adequate infrastructure, including:

- **Insufficient Facilities:** Inadequate classrooms, laboratories, and libraries hinder effective learning. Students have reported a lack of basic facilities, leading to dissatisfaction and protests.
- **Technological Shortcomings:** Limited access to essential technologies, such as internet facilities, hampers students' educational experiences. In Himachal Pradesh, students in self-financing courses often lack internet access despite repeated requests.

5. Social Inequities and Accessibility Issues

The self-financing model has exacerbated social inequities in higher education:

- **Economic Barriers:** High fees exclude economically disadvantaged students from accessing quality education, widening the socio-economic gap. In Odisha, the government's decision to cap self-financing course admissions at 20% of regular courses has led to reduced opportunities for students from lower-income backgrounds, pushing them towards more expensive private institutions.
- **Regional Disparities:** Wealthier regions attract more self-financing institutions, leading to regional imbalances in educational access and quality.

6. Regulatory Challenges and Compliance Issues

Ensuring adherence to educational standards is challenging in the self-financing sector:

- **Non-compliance with Norms:** Some institutions flout regulatory norms, such as AICTE guidelines on faculty qualifications and infrastructure requirements, compromising educational standards. In Himachal Pradesh, self-financing courses in government colleges violate AICTE norms by not recruiting regular faculty.

- **Lack of Effective Monitoring:** Regulatory bodies often lack the resources or will to enforce standards, allowing subpar institutions to operate unchecked.

7. Impact on Traditional Government Colleges

The proliferation of self-financing courses in government colleges has had mixed effects:

- **Diversion of Resources:** Focus on self-financing courses can divert resources and attention from traditional courses, affecting their quality. In Tamil Nadu, the exponential growth of self-financing sections has raised concerns about the quality of education in government-aided colleges.
- **Equity Concerns:** While self-financing courses generate revenue, they often serve students who can afford higher fees, potentially neglecting the needs of economically disadvantaged groups.

Increasing Private Role

As per AISHE 2021-22, the total number of universities in India (including university-level Institutions) was 1,168, out of which 53 were Central universities, 423 were state public universities and 391 were state private universities, institutes of national importance stood at 153, deemed private universities at 81, deemed public universities at 33, and 16 were state open universities, six were institutes set up under Acts of state legislatures, state open and Central open universities were one each.

Thus, the share of state private and deemed private universities in the total number of universities during 2021-22 was 40%, which amounts to a significant increase from 32% in 2013-14. In other words, the number of private universities of various types grew disproportionately under the current ruling dispensation.

The total number of colleges in India increased from 36,634 in 2013-14 to 42,825 in 2021-22, which implies an increase of 6,191. But out of this increase 5,976 were new private colleges while a mere 215 new public colleges were established. In other words, the orientation of the higher education policy of the ruling dispensation is to favour private higher education at the expense of public higher education.

Conclusion

Adequate amount of financing is very essential for improving its quality, then only we would be able to expect quality product from such a higher education sector. As India's higher education is the third largest amongst the world's higher education sectors and a very good number of students both from foreign and India enroll themselves to receive education under this sector, therefore considering its quality for a better future is very essential.

A quality education system would be able to create quality product which is the need of the hour for a country like India that is growing so rapidly in every sphere. We can expect that providing adequate amount of funds to the higher educational institutions would not only increase the number of students but it will also increase the quality outcomes for a better tomorrow both for the educational institution as well as the nation as a whole.

Education is delivered in both public and private institutions. However, public investment in education is important because:

1. Education is a global common good; it has direct and indirect benefits for individuals, their families, economies, societies and the planet. Moreover, the benefits of lifelong learning are inter-generational – they reach the present generation without jeopardizing future generations.
2. Education and learning are associated with other human rights and freedoms. From a human rights-based approach, States have the obligation and responsibility to guarantee the realization of the right to education. Free education reduces the cost of school and removes barriers to further education and a prosperous youth and adult life.

Securing these benefits requires commitment and long-term and predictable financing from governments to collect public revenues and mobilize and regulate funding to provide education. Unfortunately, many countries face financing gaps that can affect a whole generation of children, youth and adults, India is one among them.

For the smooth and effective functioning of higher education system of the country, educational finance is an important aspect. It is finance that can lead to the growth and development of the system like we need proper amount of water to grow a plant. Educational finance is of great value for realizing the goals of higher education and its allied aspects. The main sources for the financing of higher education in India includes government funds. The reduction in the overall education funds, particularly the substantial cut to higher education funding, has generated considerable discussion among educators, policymakers, and stakeholders. These cuts may adversely affect research quality and educational infrastructure. These reductions and allocations require careful attention to ensure that educational progress is maintained and expanded.

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